

dormancy is 10-15 d at harvest. It yields 5.5 to 6.0 t/ha.

WGL 22245 (IR579/W12708) is 80 cm tall with compact panicles. Leaves have a purple margin. It is photoperiod-insensitive with 125-d duration in monsoon and 135 d in winter. Grains are translucent. It has stem borer (SB) and

bacterial blight resistance, and yields 6.0 to 7.5 t/ha. It is recommended for release as Pothana.

WGL 26889 (IR22/12708) is a 145-d variety suitable for the monsoon season. It is SB-resistant with fine grains, and yields an average 6.0 t/ha. It is being tested in minikit trials.

WGL 20506 (Tella Hamsa/W12708) has 105-d duration and is especially suited for sowing in late monsoon, as late as mid-Aug. Grains are long and slender with a light brown husk. Yield averages 4.5 to 5.0 t/ha. □

Reaction of yellow stem borer (YSB) resistant accessions to other rice pests

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In the greenhouse we tested six accessions with resistance and moderate resistance to YSB for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH), whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), green leafhopper (GLH), leafhopper (LF), white leafhopper (WLH), and rice tungro virus (RTV).

W1263 was resistant to LF, BPH, WBPH, and GLH and moderately resistant to RTV (see table). Co 18 and

Reaction of YSB resistant accessions to major rice pests and RTV, Coimbatore, India.

Accession	Mean resistance rating ^a						
	YSB	GLH	WLH	BPH	WBPH	LF	RTV ^b
W1263	1.0 a	4.0 a	6.3 bc	3.6 a	4.3 a	1.8 a	5.0 a
Co 18	4.0 bc	6.0 ab	3.6 a	3.6 a	3.6 a	6.2 bc	7.6 c
IR13641-4	4.0 bc	7.0 bc	6.3 bc	7.6 cd	5.0 ab	6.6 c	7.0 bc
IR13639-39	4.0 bc	5.6 ab	5.6 b	5.6 b	5.0 ab	5.4 b	5.0 a
Sornavazhai	6.5 c	7.0 bc	7.6 cd	3.0 a	4.3 a	9.0 d	7.0 bc
Jaya (susceptible)	9.0 d	6.5 abc	5.0 ab	7.0 bc	6.3 ab	9.0 d	9.0 d
TN1	—	9.0 c	9.0 d	9.0 d	7.6 b	—	—

^aBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not statistically different. ^bRating scale based on field evaluation.

IR13639-39 were moderately resistant to BPH, WBPH, and WLH. IR13641-4 was moderately resistant to WBPH and

moderately susceptible to other pests. Sornavazhai was resistant to BPH and WBPH. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Tolerance for iron deficiency in rice

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Fe deficiency is a major constraint to increasing the area planted to high yielding varieties in the calcareous soils of north Bihar. Major calcareous areas are in Gopalganj, Saran, Siwan, Vaishali, Muzaffarpur, Samastipur, Begusarai, East Champaran, and parts of West Champaran and Darbhanga.

Soils have pH 7.7 to 9.8, electrical conductivity 0.1 to 4.2 dS/m, 0.1 to 1.0% organic carbon, 4 to 49% available CaCO₃, and low available P. Nurseries are dry-seeded and seedling leaves whiten in the nursery beds. Fe deficiency

symptoms are yellowing of young leaves and interveinal chlorosis which becomes whitish yellow, then ivory.

Varieties differ in susceptibility to Fe deficiency. We screened lines for Fe deficiency in the field at Pusa beginning in 1981 wet season. The first trial was non-replicated. In the next, tolerant lines were evaluated in three replications. Symptoms

were visible 15 to 20 d after seeding. IET7972 and IET7973 were tolerant of Fe deficiency. Br 34, Br 8, and TCA84 were moderately tolerant (Table 1). Most of the released varieties were susceptible to highly susceptible. Tolerant and moderately tolerant entries were photoperiod sensitive and are pureline selections from land races.

Table 1. Varietal reaction of certain elite lines to Fe deficiency, Samastipur, India.

Tolerance score	Plant infection (%)	Line
1	up to 1	IET7972 (TCA148-3), IET7973 (TCA62-31-1)
3	1 – 5	Br34, Br8, TCA84
5	5 – 25	UPR238-42-2-3, IET5882, UPR79-17, T141, NP49, IET6263
7	25 – 50	Rasi (IET1444, Pankaj, Janaki (IET9971), IET7970, KMP40, IET5883
9	50 – 100	Pusa 33, Pusa 2-21, Ratna, Rajendra Dhan 201, Sita, Jaya, Mahsuri, Saket 4, Radha (IET6261), UPR79-14, IR4568-86-1-2-3, RP1045-403-1, IR1157-52, UPR254-81-1-TCA, Br9, Katarni

Total Fe content in the leaves of tolerant and susceptible lines was unrelated to deficiency symptoms (Table 2). However, orthophenanthroline reactive Fe²⁺ content of the leaves appeared to be related with deficiency symptoms. Lines with less than 30 ppm orthophenanthroline reactive Fe²⁺ in the upper leaves were more susceptible than those with 30 to 40 ppm Fe²⁺. Lines with more than 40 ppm Fe²⁺ were tolerant.

Dry matter accumulation was significantly and positively correlated with orthophenanthroline reactive Fe²⁺ ($r = 0.90^{**}$). □

Table 2. Total dry matter content, Fe, and orthophenanthroline reactive Fe²⁺ in upper leaves of rice genotypes, Samastipur, India.

Entry	Dry matter yield (g/20 plants)	Total Fe (ppm)	Orthophenanthroline Fe ²⁺ (ppm)
IET7973	6.7	240	50
IET7972	6.3	255	42
IET5882	6.0	260	37
Pankaj	3.4	375	33
IET6263	5.2	450	36
Pusa 33	3.1	490	32
Mahsuri	2.6	337	28
Saket 4	2.7	288	30
T141	3.6	500	33

Pest control and management DISEASES

Effect of planting date on rice tungro virus (RTV) infection

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In 1980 wet season RTV infection increased in north and south Bihar. At the Pusa Experimental Farm, RTV developed the first week of Aug and attained maximum severity in Sep. In a yield evaluation trial with 16 entries planted at 3 dates, RTV infection developed at different times.

The entries were planted in a randomized block on 25 May, 9 Jun, and 24 Jun 1980 and 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted in 20- × 15-cm spacing in 7.5-m²

plots. NPK was applied at 80, 40, and 20 kg/ha. PK was applied basally and N was applied in three splits. The maximum score from three replications was used to classify entries for RTV reaction (see table). Green leafhopper population was high.

Only RP967-11-1-4-2-2 was infected on the first planting date, but many other entries developed RTV when planted on the second and third dates. Pusa 33, Pusa 2-21, Saket 4, and Ratna were resistant. Rajendra Dhan 201 and IET5656 had intermediate resistance.

The recorded infection rate show that agronomic manipulations such as early planting can minimize RTV infection in susceptible cultivars. Plant age and varying incubation period also may affect disease development. □

RTV infection of varieties planted at different dates at Pusa, India.

Entry	RTV reaction ^a		
	25 May	9 Jun	24 Jun
Pusa 33	1	1	1
Pusa 2-21	1	1	1
Govind (UPR82-1-7)	1	1	7
Saket 4 (CR44-35)	1	1	1
Ratna	1	1	1
Prasad	1	7	9
Jaya	1	7	9
IR8	1	7	9
Sita	1	7	9
Rajendra Dhan 201	1	1	5
BG90-2	1	9	9
SPR7284-57-5	1	1	9
RP967-11-1-4-2-2	7	7	9
Pankaj	1	1	7
RP975-109-2 (IET5656)	1	1	5
MRI	1	7	9

^aBy the 0-9 scale of the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

A new rice virus disease in India

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In late samba 1983, many rice varieties with yellow-orange leaves were observed in farmer fields and at the University of Coimbatore. Only a few plants showed symptoms that resembled those of rice

tungro virus (RTV). Plants had mild stunting and increased tillering. Brown planthopper (BPH) was in the fields. Infected plants were collected and transmission tests were conducted by using the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* Dist. and BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål.

Virus-free GLH adults given 4-d acquisition access feeding on source plants were transferred to 10-d-old TN1

seedlings at 2 insects/seedling for 4-d inoculation access. The inoculated plants did not develop disease symptoms (Table 1).

Second-instar nymphs from a virus-free BPH colony were released on source plants for 7-d acquisition access feeding, and then collected and released on 10-d-old TN1 seedlings at 2 insects/plant for 10-d inoculation access feeding. The inoculated plants developed yellow-